

Enhancing Pedagogical Architectures through the use of ChatGPT

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Abstract

One of the fundamental aspects of implementing new Pedagogical Architectures for Networked Learning (PANL) is proper computational support. According to studies by the proponents of PANL, such support can be significantly enhanced through the use of artificial intelligence technologies, benefiting both students and mediators. Specialized literature identifies various PANL proposals that have already been applied and evaluated in undergraduate and graduate courses. However, the implementation of AI-based solutions still faces challenges, such as the lack of suitable integration into educational applications. Recently, OpenAI introduced ChatGPT to the public, a chatbot incorporating various intelligent functionalities capable of supporting this integration. In this article, we analyze the contribution of ChatGPT-4o in supporting the PANL "Debate of Theses". We present a debate involving five students from a Brazilian public university. In the experiment, five scenarios (cases) were selected for analysis, and we discuss the specific contributions of ChatGPT-4o in each of them.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; Pedagogical Architectures; Pedagogical Mediation.

1 Introduction

Pedagogical mediation plays a crucial role in learning, whether in formal or informal contexts. In schools, this work is primarily carried out by teachers or their assistants. In classrooms with a large number of students and limited time for individualized support, mediation is often hindered, which impacts the quality of learning outcomes.

In the constructivist framework, the roles of students and teachers are redefined. The student is placed at the center of the process, responsible for interacting with both the learning objects and peers. Meanwhile, the teacher assumes new roles, such as curator and mediator. This approach allows students to engage with diverse perspectives on the topic under study, contributing to a deeper understanding of the content.

Pedagogical Architectures for Networked Learning (PANL) (Menezes & Aragón, 2018) encompass pedagogies that can accommodate flexible, adaptable, and malleable didactics suited to various thematic approaches (Menezes et al., 2021). They are based on the premise that understanding requires the creation of specific cognitive tools. This construction is fostered when individuals find a space for autonomous action and joint construction (Menezes, et. al, 2021).

Generative artificial intelligence (GenAI), which has emerged in recent years, has shown significant potential to enhance education. In our research, we have focused on exploring its use as a tool to support the mediation of learning process as foreseen in (Panceri, 2016).

This study presents a teaching experiment using the pedagogical architecture "Debate of Theses." We employed ChatGPT to analyze various aspects of the texts produced, aiming to evaluate the potential contributions of this technology in supporting teachers' mediation efforts.

2 The Pedagogical Architecture *Debate of Theses*

Within the framework of cognitive ecology, technologies are seen as components that significantly alter contexts and forms of interaction; however, their meanings and modes of use are also shaped by other components (Aragón, 2016). Thus, digital technologies are understood as part of a micro-ecosystem, always intertwined with pedagogical ideas and educational contexts (Jackson, 2013). If technologies are not conceived as integrated elements, there is a risk of imagining that simply providing them—without changing conventional pedagogical ideas—will suffice for learning to occur, or alternatively, of underestimating them by considering their use dispensable (Aragón, 2016).

In pedagogical architectures, mediation plays a fundamental role in implementing a policy that fosters debate, research, and reflection. However, mediation does not need to be limited to the teacher. While the teacher will not relinquish their role as mediator, this mediation can be performed at different levels, with the active participation of peers in a distributed manner.

The primary purpose of distributed mediation is to strengthen more horizontal and cooperative relationships among participants (Parrat-Dayán, 2007)(Camargo et al, 2012). These participants may find valuable opportunities to exercise leadership and take responsibility within their peer groups. Considering our educational culture, which tends to centralize educational processes around the figure of the teacher, this role must be learned by students—a process that can greatly benefit from engaging in collective debates within the framework of these architectures. Pedagogical architectures propose an organization of work that shifts learners to a more active position, in which they also assume mediation roles, which, in turn, are refined through practice. An example of the use of distributed mediation is the Thesis Debate architecture (Aragón, 2016).

This architecture aims to develop or deepen knowledge on a given subject cooperatively. The mediator selects a set of statements, referred to as theses, to serve as a basis for the structured debate. What we call a debate, in this case, is an asynchronous dialogue organized in stages. Initially (Stage I), each participant presents their stance (agree, disagree, partially agree, or partially disagree), supported by an argument. In Stage II, each participant reviews the argument of two fellow debaters and, in return, has their own argument reviewed by two peers. Stage III is dedicated to each participant's reflection on the reviews received. In Stage IV, each participant revisits their initial argument to (re)construct their stance, concluding with the new argumentation. The continuation of the activity can proceed in various ways, at the discretion of the mediator in cooperation with the participants.

3 Generative Artificial Intelligence

Generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) has evolved rapidly, demonstrating significant advancements in content creation, problem-solving, and personalized learning experiences. AI models have become increasingly sophisticated, integrating chain-of-thought reasoning, multimodal capabilities, and enhanced contextual understanding. AI-driven tools are now widely adopted across industries, including education, where they assist teachers in curating content, assessing student progress, and—as explored in this article—facilitating mediation in learning environments.

GenAI operates on advanced machine learning (ML) architectures, primarily deep learning models such as transformers and diffusion models. These architectures enable AI to generate coherent text, images, and other media by identifying patterns from vast datasets, processed through immense computational power. Among the fundamental technical components of GenAI are Large Language Models (LLMs), such as OpenAI's GPT series and Google's Gemini models, which leverage billions of parameters to process and generate human-like

text. These models employ self-attention mechanisms to understand context and improve response accuracy (Storey, 2025)(Floridi, 2023).

AI systems are evolving beyond simple pattern recognition toward agentic reasoning, where models actively "think" through complex problems before responding. This capability further enhances AI-driven pedagogical mediation by fostering deeper engagement and more meaningful student interactions. As AI becomes increasingly integrated into education, researchers emphasize bias mitigation and ethical AI development to ensure fair and responsible use. Techniques such as algorithmic transparency and human-in-the-loop oversight help maintain AI reliability (Storey, 2025).

These advancements position generative AI as a powerful tool for pedagogical mediation, enabling personalized learning feedback and improving student-teacher interactions.

4 The Experiment

Text production in a Debate of Theses (Aragón, Menezes, & Castro, 2022) is rich and extensive. To handle different analyses of the debate results, the support of computational assistants is often necessary.

To demonstrate the type of intelligent support that ChatGPT can offer, we conducted a Debate of Theses with the participation of three undergraduate students from a Production Engineering program, all of whom were Scientific Initiation scholarship holders at a public institution in Brazil. The debate took place in an online digital environment specifically developed for activities of this nature (<http://debatedeteses.com.br/>). Table 1 presents a description of the debate conducted.

Table 1. Description of the Experiment

<p>Debate – Project Management</p> <p>Description: Learning about project management in a cooperative way. Debate asynchronously with your peers to deepen your understanding of project management.</p> <p>Mediator(s): (omitted for review)</p> <p>Participants: 5 debaters</p> <p>Theses: 3 theses were created: (i) Scope changes will not harm the project; (ii) If the team has already had a successful experience in a project, then the next project will also succeed if they follow the same steps; (iii) If a project is on schedule and within budget, it will achieve good results.</p> <p>GENAI used for analysis: ChatGPT 4o</p>
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The queries conducted are part of a selection of features that may contribute to supporting the mediation of a debate. After each query was presented, we held a brief discussion on the result provided by the generative AI considered (ChatGPT 4o).

To illustrate the different aspects of the texts produced, we selected "Thesis (i): Scope changes will not harm the project" along with the contributions of three debaters. Our aim was to evaluate potential contributions of technology in supporting the teacher's mediation work. To this end, we identified specific functionalities of ChatGPT that could assist in facilitating debate mediation. After presenting each case, we conducted a brief discussion on the results provided by ChatGPT-4o.

Case 1: Coherence Between the Argument and the Thesis

<p>Context: Consider the initial argument of Participant 1 (P1) regarding Thesis 1:</p> <p><i>The change in project scope, by itself, is not necessarily harmful; it can indeed negatively affect the project, especially if the goal increases its complexity and/or the deadline is moved closer to the present moment. However, the opposite cases can benefit a project that would otherwise be delayed or lack resources.</i></p>
<p>Request: Analyze the correlation of the argument in relation to the content of Thesis 1.</p>
<p>ChatGPT Response: Yes, the initial argument text shows a good correlation with the proposed thesis because it directly discusses the consequences (negative or positive) of scope changes on the project, which is the subject of the thesis.</p>
<p>Discussion: The coherence between the argument and the thesis, as identified by the GenAI, may indicate to the mediator that there is no need for intervention regarding the initial positioning. However, in cases where incoherence is detected, the mediator can perform problem-posing interventions to guide the participant in seeking coherence, which is important for the continuity of the debate.</p>

Case 2: Authenticity of Participants' Argumentations

<p>Context: Consider the initial argumentations of the other two participants:</p> <p>Initial argumentation of Participant P2: This type of change affects what is scheduled to be executed, which is clearly a problem for the organization of the project as a whole.</p> <p>Initial argumentation of Participant P3: Although scope changes happen very frequently, this requires a great deal of flexibility from those executing the project. Therefore, depending on the variables, the team may not be able to adapt, and the project may suffer negative consequences—such as compromising the delivery deadline or increasing its cost. For this reason, it is important for the manager to anticipate the factors that may influence the execution of the project and to plan its scope while already considering possible future changes.</p>
<p>Request: Verify whether there is any evidence of plagiarism among the initial argumentations of the three participants.</p>
<p>ChatGPT's response: There is no evidence of plagiarism among the initial argumentations of the three participants. Although all address the same topic and naturally share some common ideas (impacts of scope changes), the texts are distinct in form, structure, and development.</p>
<p>Discussion: A recurring concern among teachers is the possibility that students may reproduce already published texts or even consult a Generative AI tool. In this case, rather than being a source of plagiarism, AI can serve as a means of verifying authorship. The use of the Thesis Debate architecture, particularly in its initial argumentation stage, requires participants to express their ideas, reflecting their prior knowledge. To assess whether participants' knowledge has progressed, it is imperative that the initial stance be authentic.</p>

Case 3: Contributions of the Reviewers

<p>Context: Now consider the text from the second reviewer (R2) to Participant P1:</p> <p><i>The point presented is consistent with what is stated in the thesis, but it was necessary to reread it several times to understand what the argument was trying to convey—especially the last sentence.</i></p>
<p>Request: Analyze the contribution to P1's reflections with a view to deepening their analysis, as well as the cordiality of the text.</p>

ChatGPT’s response: R2’s review is polite and provides a relevant comment regarding textual clarity. However, it lacks deeper analytical input to help P1 strengthen their argument in terms of content, not just form.

Discussion: For knowledge advancement within the proposed pedagogical architecture, it is essential that exchanges (dialogues) occur among participants. The confrontation of ideas requires justification of what has been argued, and when such justifications are insufficient, doubts arise. Through actions taken to resolve these doubts (such as readings, reflections, etc.), participants reconstruct their prior knowledge, leading to new ideas. Considering the importance of interindividual exchanges, the mediator intervenes to ensure that this dynamic unfolds within the timeframe established for this stage and provides quality materials to support the debate among participants.

Case 4: Evolution of the Argumentations

Context: After interacting with their peers, participants present a new stance and argumentation for each thesis in Stage 4.

Still considering Thesis 1, below are Participant P2’s stance and argumentation in Stage 1 and Stage 4.

Stage 1

Stance: Partially disagree.

Argumentation: Although scope changes happen very frequently, this requires a great deal of flexibility from those executing the project. Therefore, depending on the variables, the team may not be able to adapt, and the project may suffer negative consequences—such as compromising the delivery deadline or increasing its cost. For this reason, it is important for the manager to anticipate the factors that may influence the execution of the project and to plan its scope while already considering possible future changes.

Stage 4

Stance: Partially disagree.

Argumentation: Although scope changes may be inevitable, they require a great deal of flexibility. Therefore, depending on the variables, the execution team may not be able to adapt and may face negative consequences—for example, affecting the delivery deadline and/or increasing the project’s cost. Thus, it is up to the project manager, during planning, to consider the factors that may influence its execution, incorporating the observed information into the project scope. This makes it possible to maintain greater control over the project and avoid changes in the future.

Request: Analyze the evolution of their argumentation.

ChatGPT’s response: The participant maintained their stance and the central ideas that scope changes can be problematic and require managerial attention. In Stage 4, there was qualitative improvement by adding a more practical and explicit recommendation to incorporate these analyses into the scope itself. The final argumentation is more coherent and flows better, although a small grammatical adjustment is needed in the opening.

Discussion: Considering the challenges that mediators typically face in mapping each participant’s learning trajectory—especially in groups with a larger number of participants—AI can play a facilitating role in monitoring the process and providing support for assessment. With this support, the mediator can carry out interventions to improve the quality of the argumentations, such as suggesting reference materials.

Case 5: Convergences and Divergences of the 3 Participants

Context: Now consider the final stance and argumentation of the 3 participants regarding Stage 4.

Participant P1

Stance: Partially disagree.

Argumentation: The change in the project's scope, by itself, is not necessarily harmful; it can indeed negatively affect the project, especially if the goal increases its complexity and/or the deadline is moved closer to the present moment. However, the opposite cases can benefit a project that would otherwise be delayed or lacking resources.

Participant P2

Stance: Partially disagree.

Argumentation: This type of change affects what is scheduled to be executed, which is clearly a problem for the organization of the project as a whole. However, scope changes can be made to adjust the project's progress in light of unforeseen events and possible improvements.

Participant P3

Stance: Partially disagree.

Argumentation: Although scope changes may be inevitable, they require a great deal of flexibility. Therefore, depending on the variables, the execution team may not be able to adapt and may face negative consequences—for example, affecting the delivery deadline and/or increasing the project's cost. Thus, it is up to the project manager, during planning, to consider the factors that may influence its execution, incorporating the observed information into the project scope. This makes it possible to maintain greater control over the project and avoid future changes.

Request: Analyze the convergences and divergences in the argumentation.

ChatGPT's response: All participants maintain a generally convergent line of reasoning: scope changes are generally problematic but should not be viewed as invariably harmful.

P3 stands out by offering a more technically detailed solution (proactive planning and control), while P1 and P2 are simpler and more descriptive.

P2, although more concise, introduces a new point in Stage 4 (the acceptance of changes as adjustments), while P1 almost entirely repeats their initial argumentation.

Discussion: In this case, AI support involves mapping both individuals and the group regarding the knowledge generated in the debate. In this way, it assists the mediator in assessing both individual learning and the outcomes of the architecture's application. Furthermore, it can indicate to the mediator aspects of the debated topic that may need to be revisited.

5 Discussion

This investigation was informed by pedagogical practices conducted at basic, undergraduate, and graduate levels. Depending on the number of participants, the mediation process is often hindered by time constraints, limiting the observation of more abstract aspects of students' reasoning. A significant portion of instructional time is typically devoted to analyzing structural elements, such as thematic deviations, redundant arguments, and basic textual organization.

The experiment reported here demonstrated the feasibility of developing computational filters based on carefully designed natural language prompts. These tools facilitate the analysis of preliminary textual features and support pedagogical mediation at a conceptual level, thereby fostering the identification of students' intellectual development.

In the specific context of a thesis debate, the goal is to provide formative feedback aimed at enhancing students' awareness of the discursive implications of a thesis, while also promoting engagement with multiple perspectives. These deeper insights are often constrained by the need to first address structural issues, delaying more meaningful semantic interpretation. The findings suggest that GenAI can assist in filtering preliminary aspects of the analysis, allowing educators to focus on higher-level conceptual mediation.

Based on the findings of this study, a new version of the "Thesis Debate" platform is being developed to incorporate functionalities that strengthen and better support the role of the mediator.

6 Concluding Remarks

In this article, we discussed some of the possibilities that so-called Generative Artificial Intelligences demonstrate for contributing to education, both as intelligent support for teacher mediation and for distributed mediation. We also provided examples and presented situations in which GenAI acts as a companion to the student. It is not about replacing the teacher's mediation or distributed mediation, nor about substituting students' learning efforts, but rather about using GenAI as an element that forms part of the students' learning ecosystem, enabling "dialogues" that may stimulate cognitive development.

Regarding the monitoring and analysis of learning, we observe that GenAI can play a role, as it allows the teacher to organize the interactions that occur among students and between students and the teacher, in addition to supporting the monitoring of individual and group development. Among other possibilities, we highlight that GenAI can reveal gaps in students' knowledge, inconsistencies in their arguments, and conceptual changes (learning) that unfold during the course of pedagogical architecture.

It is also important to highlight that the analyzed situations represent moments during or between the stages of the Debate of Theses, where the mediator can contribute to the quality of the discussion. Of course, many other situations anticipated in Panceri (2016) still need to be examined, particularly regarding support for collective synthesis. This report is part of an ongoing investigation aimed at developing new functionalities for the <http://debatedeteses.com.br/> platform to support Networked Learning Pedagogical Architectures (PANL).

The ethical challenges associated with the development and implementation of artificial intelligence must not be underestimated (Floridi, 2025). The proposal presented in this article was developed alongside ethical reflections and precautions that considered the inherent biases and limitations of AI. Measures were taken to critically analyse the responses generated by the AI, with the aim of ensuring their appropriateness and evaluating their potential to support teachers in their pedagogical mediation. This, therefore, is not a naive use of AI, but a deliberate effort to explore ways of employing it to enhance educational practices.

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